

The search for SARS origins – historical context

Preface to “Scrutinizing the extraordinary mosaic evolution of SARS-like coronaviruses” doi://10.5281/zenodo.13476370

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At the turn of the millennium, there were just two coronaviruses known to infect humans – 229E and OC43. These share common ancestors with animal coronaviruses but are thought to have diverged long ago (estimates range between 150 years, to hundreds of thousands of years ago). Coronaviruses were thought to be highly specialized, each infecting only a single, or small number of related host species after which they were often named¹. Coronaviruses (with some exceptions) usually bind with protein receptors whose sequence varies between different host species. To infect the cells of a different species usually entails some adaptation by mutation. In contrast influenza variants bind with forms of sialic acids that are ubiquitously expressed in birds and mammals (albeit in different amounts through the respiratory system, still providing a hurdle to species switching).

In the late 1990s there was burgeoning scientific interest in mechanisms by which host and system tropism could be made to change in a lab environment. Scientists at Colorado Neurological Institute found that using intracerebral inoculation they were able to infect primates with a neurotropic form of mouse coronavirus MHV causing demyelination in the central nervous system². UNC’s Ralph Baric found that inducing persistent infection with MHV (120 to 210 days) produced mutants with an expanded host range, at least in cell lines³. Scientists at Utrecht University under Peter Rottier switched the spike gene of MHV, with that of feline coronavirus FIPV, and found the artificial recombinant could now infect cat

¹ Kathryn Holmes *Coronaviruses (Encyclopedia of Virology)*

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7150129/>

² Ronald S. Murray, Guang-Yun Cai, Kristen Hoel, J.-Y. Zhang, Kenneth F. Soike, Gary F. Cabirac *Coronavirus infects and causes demyelination in primate central nervous system*

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S004268229290757G>

³ Ralph S. Baric, Eileen Sullivan, Lisa Hensley, Boyd Yount, Wan Chen *Persistent Infection Promotes Cross-Species Transmissibility of Mouse Hepatitis Virus* <https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/jvi.73.1.638-649.1999>

cells, but not mice⁴. There were also breakthroughs in reverse genetic systems, enabling scientists to work with smaller genome segments before re-assembly^{5,6,7,8}.

Towards the end of 2002, SARS broke out. Unlike the other two known human coronaviruses, which were endemic “common cold” viruses, SARS was highly virulent (at least in some patients), and seemed capable of rapid spread, particularly by “super-spreaders”. The potential for coronaviruses as a biological weapon didn’t go unnoticed in the US. NIAID, under Anthony Fauci, was handed responsibility for US biodefense, which had previously been a US Department of Defense remit. With it came a budget for searching for novel zoonotic pathogens with potential military or terrorist use. Zoonotic coronaviruses with potential to spillover to humans and possibly even cause a pandemic, were high on the list. Contracts to private organizations such as EcoHealth Alliance were assigned from a budget allocation for “Countering the Threat of Weapons of Mass Destruction”.

But unlike SARS-CoV-2, a possible artificial origin of SARS attracted little public attention in the West, because its impact was largely contained. In China however, official pronouncements on SARS were understandably distrusted, and rumors abounded - including that it was a man-made bioweapon. The most credible proponent of this theory was General Xu Dezhong, senior epidemiologist from the 4th Military Medical Hospital. Xu’s team was involved in contact tracing and epidemiology during the epidemic, and he was well-known in China for his media appearances⁹.

Xu has been misrepresented by Western media as something of a biowarfare “Dr Strangelove”. This is due to his co-editorship of a volume of papers, a review of biowarfare principles and technology, that includes a chapter on his artificial origin hypothesis¹⁰. But it’s not evident from this that he was a proponent of biowarfare. In fact, Xu was troubled that epidemiological data suggested an unnatural origin, and greatly concerned that the possibility wasn’t being investigated by Chinese authorities. Xu didn’t accuse a specific party (it’s been incorrectly asserted in the media that he sought to blame the

⁴ Lili Kuo, Gert-Jan Godeke, Martin J. B. Raamsman, Paul S. Masters, Peter J. M. Rottier ***Retargeting of Coronavirus by Substitution of the Spike Glycoprotein Ectodomain: Crossing the Host Cell Species Barrier*** <https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/jvi.74.3.1393-1406.2000>

⁵ Paul S. Masters ***Reverse Genetics of The Largest RNA Viruses*** <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0065352708603516>

⁶ Fernando Almazán, José M. González, Zoltan Péntzes, Ander Izeta, Enrique Calvo, Juan Plana-Durán, and Luis Enjuanes ***Engineering the largest RNA virus genome as an infectious bacterial artificial chromosome*** <https://www.pnas.org/doi/full/10.1073/pnas.97.10.5516>

⁷ Rosa Casais, Volker Thiel, Stuart G. Siddell, David Cavanagh, and Paul Britton ***Reverse Genetics System for the Avian Coronavirus Infectious Bronchitis Virus*** <https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/jvi.75.24.12359-12369.2001>

⁸ Volker Thiel, Jens Herold, Barbara Schelle, Stuart G Siddell ***Infectious RNA transcribed in vitro from a cDNA copy of the human coronavirus genome cloned in vaccinia virus*** <https://www.microbiologyresearch.org/content/journal/jgv/10.1099/0022-1317-82-6-1273>

⁹ Dezhong Xu, Huimin Sun, Haixia Su, Lei Zhang, Jingxia Zhang, Bo Wang, Rui Xu ***SARS coronavirus without reservoir originated from an unnatural evolution, experienced the reverse evolution, and finally disappeared in the world*** https://journals.lww.com/cmj/Fulltext/2014/07050/SARS_coronavirus_without_reservoir_originated_from.24.aspx

¹⁰ Xu Dezhong and Li Feng ***Unnatural Origin Of Sars And New Species Of Man Made Viruses As Genetic Bioweapons*** <https://dogsbreakfast.substack.com/api/v1/file/98826808-14de-43bc-b0bc-42988cca4370.pdf>

US¹¹). Having tried unsuccessfully to get Chinese authorities to take his theory seriously, he then tried to get papers published in western medical journals, again unsuccessfully.

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Dear Dr Xu,

Thank you for your letters of 4 May and 19 June 2013, addressed to Dr [REDACTED] Director-General of [REDACTED]. We are grateful for your consideration and support. Coronaviruses continue to pose threats to people's health.

As I am sure that you know, most recently, our Member States and the World Health Organization have been engaged in the response to the Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV). Updated information on that outbreak is available on the WHO website, http://www.who.int/csr/disease/coronavirus_infections/en/index.html

Best wishes in your academic endeavors.

Your sincerely,

Y-Y

[REDACTED]
Assistance Director-General for

Xu also wrote to the WHO, requesting that they investigate, but was rebuffed. The Director-General of WHO at the time was Margaret Chan, who had been Hong Kong's Director of Health during SARS. Xu wrote a highly personal letter to Chan, addressed her deferentially, reminded her of where they had crossed paths, and expressed pride in her being the first Chinese WHO Director-General "shouldering the important task of protecting the health of all mankind". In still relatively liberal Hong Kong, Chan received less respect. She had been publicly criticized for her handling of SARS. A Legislative Council enquiry admonished her for not raising the alert quickly, for being too trusting of PRC authorities, and for not preparing for the inevitable spread of SARS to Hong Kong¹².

That Chan's curt, delegated response to Xu refers to MERS wasn't merely to say that WHO was busy with other things, but to emphasize that SARS was by then no longer unique. MERS is another novel human coronavirus that first emerged round that time (June, 2012) presumed to have spilled from camels, but - like SARS - its precursors are bat viruses. And, like SARS, MERS genome suggests a recombinant origin. Overall, MERS genome most closely resembles viruses found in African bats (e.g. NeoCoV, discovered in South Africa). But in the important spike gene it is more similar to those that had been found in southern China - HKU4 and HKU5¹³. This echoed the understanding of SARS genome at the time. Though much of the SARS genome most closely resembled bat viruses found in China, the

¹¹ Stephen Chen *The Chinese book at the bottom of Sars bioweapons claims that emerged amid coronavirus pandemic*

<https://www.scmp.com/news/china/science/article/3132949/chinese-book-bottom-sars-bioweapons-claims>

¹² Chan Wai Yin, Ma Shu Yun *The Making of a Chinese Head of the Who: A Study of the Media Discourse on Margaret Chan's Contest for the who Director-Generalship and its Implications for the Collective Memory of Sars*
<https://doi.org/10.2190/hs.39.3.i>

¹³ Jarel Elgin Tolentino, Spyros Lytras, Jumpei Ito & Kei Sato *Recombination analysis on the receptor switching event of MERS-CoV and its close relatives: implications for the emergence of MERS-CoV*
<https://virologyj.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12985-024-02358-2>

important RBD attachment region was most similar to a virus that was sampled in Bulgaria, BM48-31¹⁴, whose sequence was published to GenBank in November 2009. If we exclude the viruses that are the subject of this investigation, then the viruses *currently known* that are most similar to SARS in the RBD are some of those sampled in the UK in 2021¹⁵ - although these still have key differences to SARS.

In the case of MERS, an international group of experts was quickly convened, and the name was agreed to emphasize its place of first emergence in the Middle East¹⁶. Today there is still no consensus agreement of MERS origin, and sporadic outbreaks continue. It's been suggested by University of NSW Professor Raina Macintyre that the epidemiology of MERS is inconsistent with a natural origin¹⁷.

MERS wasn't the first novel human coronavirus to emerge after SARS. In January 2004, six months after the epidemic was declared over, a handful of isolated SARS cases were detected in Guangdong. At the same time another novel human coronavirus, HKU1, was discovered in Hong Kong in a patient with pneumonia who had recently returned from Guangdong¹⁸. Although symptoms are rarely severe, this "common cold" virus has become endemic world-wide, most adults in western countries are seropositive. With the addition of NL63 (another "common cold" virus, isolated in Netherlands in 2004^{19,20}), MERS and, most recently SARS-CoV-2, the count of known human coronaviruses went from two in 2001, to seven in 2019. NL63's detection may have been the result of advances which enabled scientists to retrospectively identify pathogens already circulating. But there is strong evidence the others emerged recently.

In late 2012, a group affiliated with Institut Pasteur Shanghai, and Guangzhou Institute of Respiratory Diseases, submitted a paper on the origin of SARS, claiming SARS jumped directly from bats to humans

¹⁴ Jan Felix Drexler, Florian Gloza-Rausch, Jörg Glende, Victor Max Corman, Doreen Muth...Marcel Alexander Müller, Hongkui Deng, Georg Herrler, Christian Drosten ***Genomic Characterization of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-Related Coronavirus in European Bats and Classification of Coronaviruses Based on Partial RNA-Dependent RNA Polymerase Gene Sequences***
<https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/jvi.00650-10>

¹⁵ Ternenge Aapa, Amy J. Withers, Ceri Staley¹, Adam Blanchard¹, Malcolm Bennett¹, Samantha Bremner-Harrison, Elizabeth A. Chadwick, Frank Hailer, Stephen W. R. Harrison, Matthew Loose, Fiona Mathews and Rachael Tarlinton ***Sarbecoviruses of British horseshoe bats; sequence variation and epidemiology***
<https://www.microbiologyresearch.org/content/journal/jgv/10.1099/jgv.0.001859>

¹⁶ Raoul J. de Groot, Susan C. Baker, Ralph S. Baric, Caroline S. Brown, Christian Drosten, Luis Enjuanes, Ron A. M. Fouchier, Monica Galiano, Alexander E. Gorbalenya, Ziad A. Memish, Stanley Perlman, Leo L. M. Poon, Eric J. Snijder, Gwen M. Stephens, Patrick C. Y. Woo, Ali M. Zaki, Maria Zambon, John Ziebuhr ***Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV): Announcement of the Coronavirus Study Group***
<https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/jvi.01244-13>

¹⁷ C. Raina MacIntyre ***The discrepant epidemiology of Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV)***
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10669-014-9506-5>

¹⁸ Patrick C. Y. Woo, Susanna K. P. Lau, Chung-ming Chu, Kwok-hung Chan, Hoi-wah Tsoi, Yi Huang, Beatrice H. L. Wong, Rosana W. S. Poon, James J. Cai, Wei-kwang Luk, Leo L. M. Poon, Samson S. Y. Wong, Yi Guan, J. S. Malik Peiris, Kwok-yung Yuen ***Characterization and Complete Genome Sequence of a Novel Coronavirus, Coronavirus HKU1, from Patients with Pneumonia*** <https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/jvi.79.2.884-895.2005>

¹⁹ Lia van der Hoek, Krzysztof Pyrc, Maarten F. Jebbink, Wilma Vermeulen-Oost, Ron J. M. Berkhout, Katja C. Wolthers, Pauline M. E. Wertheim-van Dillen, Jos Kaandorp, Joke Spaargaren & Ben Berkhout ***Identification of a new human coronavirus*** <https://www.nature.com/articles/nm1024>

²⁰ Ron A. M. Fouchier, Nico G. Hartwig, Theo M. Bestebroer, Berend Niemeyer, Jan C. de Jong, James H. Simon, and Albert D. M. E. Osterhaus ***A previously undescribed coronavirus associated with respiratory disease in humans***
<https://www.pnas.org/doi/full/10.1073/pnas.0400762101>

(i.e. not via civets). They estimated the date of first spillover to 1991, followed by a period of adaptation, and the emergence of human SARS in 1998. But the paper was never published. A pre-print posted to ArXiv²¹ has a curious comment that the paper had been accepted for publication by PLoS ONE, but later this was rescinded, and further suggests that some outside interference. Senior author Zhong Nanshan is a popular hero of the SARS epidemic²², particularly for ignoring the official declaration that it was a bacterial disease, and should only be treated with antibiotics. Based on success with his own patients, Zhong proscribed and advocated the use of cortisone, which later became part of the standard protocol.

SARS-CoV originated from bats in 1998 and may still exist in humans

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In May 2013, WIV submitted the paper announcing new virus discoveries that “proved” that bats were the reservoir species, which was published 30th October 2013, and the sequences soon afterwards²³. Xu’s group remained unconvinced, and published further papers disputing that WIV’s sequences constituted proof, as they lacked important identifying genetic features. WIV (and others) responded with further sequences, and a paper which claimed all the “building blocks” for SARS could be found in a single cave in Yunnan²⁴, and that recombination was so frequent that SARS would have at some point evolved - even if the direct progenitor couldn’t be found. Although this is an extraordinary claim epidemiologically and virologically, objections were subdued. Perhaps this is due to the perceived support of international experts like Ralph Baric, or perhaps stronger political pressure in China. In any case it is widely believed to be the “scientific consensus” by those unaware of the political backdrop and

²¹ Ailin Tao, Yuyi Huang, Peilu Li, Jun Liu, Nanshan Zhong, Chiyu Zhang ***SARS-CoV originated from bats in 1998 and may still exist in humans*** <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1305/1305.2659.pdf>

²² ***SARS hero named among China's 10 best scientists, technicians***
https://web.archive.org/web/20101220160039/http://news.xinhuanet.com/english2010/china/2010-12/06/c_13637285.htm

²³ Xing-Yi Ge, Jia-Lu Li, Xing-Lou Yang, Aleksei A. Chmura, Guangjian Zhu, Jonathan H. Epstein, Jonna K. Mazet, Ben Hu, Wei Zhang, Cheng Peng, Yu-Ji Zhang, Chu-Ming Luo, Bing Tan, Ning Wang, Yan Zhu, Gary Crameri, Shu-Yi Zhang, Lin-Fa Wang, Peter Daszak & Zheng-Li Shi ***Isolation and characterization of a bat SARS-like coronavirus that uses the ACE2 receptor***
<https://www.nature.com/articles/nature12711>

²⁴ Ben Hu, Lei-Ping Zeng, Xing-Lou Yang, Xing-Yi Ge, Wei Zhang, Bei Li, Jia-Zheng Xie, Xu-Rui Shen, Yun-Zhi Zhang, Ning Wang, Dong-Sheng Luo, Xiao-Shuang Zheng, Mei-Niang Wang, Peter Daszak, Lin-Fa Wang, Jie Cui, Zheng-Li Shi ***Discovery of a rich gene pool of bat SARS-related coronaviruses provides new insights into the origin of SARS coronavirus***
<https://journals.plos.org/plospathogens/article?id=10.1371/journal.ppat.1006698>

the challenges it poses to long-standing theories of molecular evolution²⁵. In turn, it has been used as precedent for a similarly radical evolutionary origin of SARS-CoV-2.

While some scientists question the natural origin of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, few have critically re-examined the evidence for the first SARS (let alone MERS or HKU1). Almost all the relevant sequence data is published by the PRC state entities WIV and the Academy of Military Medical Science, the PRC funded State Key Lab of Emerging Infectious Disease at HKU, and a few individuals and institutions closely associated them. This paper was started as an attempt to summarize the key papers and sequences to increase awareness of the context. In doing so an unusually cohesive scientific narrative emerged. Discoveries necessary to explain peculiar genomic features occur in sequence with such timeliness, it suggests more than serendipity. Genomic features within the sequence data have been placed with unnatural precision. The possibility of human artifice should be properly considered, before we revise our understanding of evolution.

²⁵ David Cyranoski *SARS outbreak linked to Chinese bat cave* <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-017-07766-9>